

INFLUENCE OF ECONOMIC REFORMS ON THE SPIRITUAL IMAGE OF THE INDIVIDUAL

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Annotation: the issue of economic reforms being carried out in Uzbekistan and its impact on the spiritual image of the individual is analyzed. The role and importance of socio-spiritual factors in solving economic problems has been studied.

Key words: economy, globalization, value, society, spirituality, personality spirituality, spiritual maturity, integration, financial culture.

Where there is a spiritual and spiritual crisis, it is a fact that economic progress cannot be achieved. A person of high spirituality, temporarily does not stumble in the face of existing economic difficulties, he acts with perspective, is able to turn productive work on the path of his children, nationality and the bright future of the country into the basic principle of his lifestyle. This forms the meaning of the path taken in Uzbekistan on the influence of the spiritual factor on economic development in the transition to market relations.

Human productive activity has not only economic, but also its own spiritual aspects. Giving the same great importance to the development of spirituality with the economy, society provides the basis for its sustainable development without major social conflicts and contradictions. In a country where the harmony and harmony of economy and spirituality are ensured, it is easy to achieve the desired goal in development, progress. From the lessons of history, this is clear and clear that when a state or society does not focus solely on the production and reproduction of material goods and does not think about satisfying the spiritual needs of the person who creates it, it will definitely face degradation and crisis. Without spirituality, without economy and economy, spirituality cannot reach a high level.

Before solving economic issues, tasks, and then dealing with spirituality, the thoughts of some politicians and theorists are completely wrong, confirming at every step that life itself today can only harm in the process of building a new society, a new life.

In his work “high spirituality-invincible power”, I.Karimov said, pointing out that the harmony of economy and spirituality is one of the main factors determining the progress of society: “...if we compare the material and spiritual world necessary for the realization of human - specific aspirations, for his conscious life, with the two wings of a bird flying in a leisurely flight... is appropriate.

Because any economic issues are solved by the owners of certain spirituality and enlightenment. The more economically developed the country, the higher the morale and enlightenment in this country. The economic strength of a country with high morale and enlightenment will also be high. It means that a person with a high level of spirituality and enlightenment deeply feels the responsibility imposed on him in the face of the country, the country, the people. For this country, country, people, an honest, selfless Creator, with creative work, a keen sense that he must contribute to his flight to the heights. Thus, progress is easy in a society in which high spirituality and enlightenment are associated with high economy, and high economy with high spirituality and enlightenment.

Some people claim that in the conditions of a free market economy, the value of spiritual, educational and moral values will decrease, culture and spirituality will become secondary things, and spiritual poverty will increase. It is completely inappropriate to oppose the free market economy and spirituality, on the contrary, as we said above, they complement each other, because only a spiritually healthy and strong society can be ready for reforms.

During the years of independence, economic and spiritual processes have been developing in a mutually harmonious manner, serving as a solid guarantee of political and social stability and development in our country.

Therefore, spirituality and economy do not negate each other, but strengthen each other, interact and develop. Currently, we are moving to a new, higher stage of economic reforms, which means that production sectors will start working and economic growth will take place. This has a positive effect on the development of science, culture and spirituality.

Our ancestors correctly understood that economy, spirituality and enlightenment are closely related. Based on this, they developed a whole complex of moral standards, in other words, a code of ethics, about a perfect, highly spiritual person. It is based on the main core and aspect of a person's heart: the danger of uncleanness, impurity, injustice, honesty and piety in market relations, sincerity in relation to the customer, gentle treatment, and the desire to find the customer's satisfaction.

A person with a high spirituality does not betray the rights of others, the property of the state, the community, he is loyal, he does not spare himself to sacrifice his life for the country, country, people. On the contrary, spiritually poor people are impure, swindlers, bribe takers, thieves, swindlers, indifferent to the interests of the Motherland and the nation.

In the future, Uzbekistan should surprise the world not only with its highly developed economy, but also with its educated and spiritually mature children. We can achieve this only if we attach importance to the joint development of the economy, spirituality, and enlightenment.

Only spiritual, enlightened, and believing people will be true patriots who create wealth with their honest work, seek, be honest, hardworking, entrepreneurs, and heal the country's pain. A country and a society with such citizens will continuously move up the ladder of economic development.

In the implementation of market reforms in our country, it is a priority to improve the employment of the population, increase its well-being, as well as to encourage the support and development of small business and private

entrepreneurship, service and household industries as the most important direction of the development of our economy. designated as one of the directions. Because these sectors have been performing a special locomotive task in solving the problems of population employment and increasing its income, which are the most acute for us, and in making a significant contribution to filling our domestic market with consumer goods.

The basis of the market economy and its development is the entrepreneur and his activities. After all, the demand of the market economy is entrepreneurship and business. What is an entrepreneur and entrepreneurship? The question of what an entrepreneur's spirituality should be should not leave anyone indifferent, especially our young people who strive for it.

Therefore, the path of market economy chosen by independent Uzbekistan is promising because it requires from everyone extreme entrepreneurship, promptness, thrift, perseverance, patience when the time comes, coolness, and the eye of the task in every situation. requires knowledge, extreme care in handling, separating and distinguishing the form and meaning of each word, etc.

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